
SO I WON'T FORGET

Chos skyong skyabs མོས་སྐྱོང་སྐྱུང་ལ། (Qiejiangjia 切江加)*

1

A chilly, windy, snowy midwinter day. You are in your blind maternal grandfather's bed in the corner of your family's black yak-hair tent. The lower part of the tent constantly trembles, buffeted by the strong winds, like a giant bird flapping its wings. An occasional puff of wind-driven snow circulates everywhere in the tent. Heavy snow covers the grassland. A thick haze has swallowed the upper part of the nearby mountains. Our sheep flock bleats as they move here and there, unable to get to the grass under the heavy snow. The wind howls, and the sky grows darker. It will probably soon snow again.

2

In the summer pasture. Twenty children swim in a pool created by a small dam on a creek near the local families. XX accidentally unleashes their dog. It mauls two children badly. You pull your little sister away from the danger. YY is enraged. Serial conflicts follow between the XX and YY families. Frequent fighting and scolding. The community is saturated in a stressful, unpleasant atmosphere.

3

Your Grade Three primary school math teacher. An unmarried, unhappy young woman with a cold face from an agricultural area kicks the door open 'bang' with her black high-heeled shoes. She rushes to the teacher's platform, bleating at the students in her goatish voice, constantly thumping the rostrum with a bamboo stick. Tshe ring's bleeding hands and calves, 1, 2, 3, ... 97, 98, 99, 100. Tears without end dribble down his cheeks. His hands become red, redder, numb, number, and bloody. He loses consciousness. The bamboo stick becomes warm. He didn't recite the multiplication table correctly, but that's not the reason for the beating.

* Chos skyong skyabs. 2023. So I Won't Forget. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 63:384-387.

4

Sgrol ma mtsho joins your Grade Six primary school class. Pale face, easy to communicate with, nice clean clothes. She sits in front of your desk and turns around to chat with you during break time. Tension grows - your thoughts of her muddle your mind. Shy, nervous near her outside the classroom, mesmerized by her actions, you pretend to ignore her.

5

Your uncle and his son buy a new car in the provincial capital and head home. Then a terrible accident not very far from their home. Their new white car folded, smashed, blood everywhere. Both are taken to a hospital. In beds. Heads covered with gauze, one broken jaw, two broken legs, a broken arm, and dangling IV bottles.

6

The local primary school. Autumn, your tent. Uncle S, who lives with his wife's family, rents grassland near us, so we are neighbors in Ldum lhas. Uncle S buys a heavy, very-used motorcycle that produces dark, smelly smoke clouds. How many yaks or sheep are exchanged for it? That tireless fascinating machine can carry two or three people into the distance. Stranger still, its two wheels are in a straight line, but it remains upright.

How you yearn for Uncle S to allow you and your cousins to ride behind him after he masters motorcycle driving. After about ten days of diligent practice, Uncle S is confident enough to do that.

In the morning, that noisy machine is just a big, heavy piece of metal that Uncle has to wake up by pouring several kettles of hot water on the engine before trying to start it. If that doesn't work, the next step is pushing the motorcycle up a slope, riding it down, and popping the clutch. We do this three or four times, eight or nine times on cold mornings, before the motorcycle coughs, sputters, and finally roars to life.

When he goes to town, you and your cousins sit behind him for one or two kilometers and then walk back home. In the afternoon, you all watch, and once you see and hear him in the distance, you run to him and ride home behind him.

7

The year of fighting. A dark summer night. You wake up suddenly to your mother and aunt praying behind the adobe stove in our black yak-hair tent. The stove's flickering flames illuminate their anxious, worried faces. Seven families in your camp. The men and older boys all left to fight in the evening, leaving the women, children, and elders. The old neighbor woman's loud prayers and your mother and aunt's preparations to flee worry you the most. Your mother and aunt rush about, preparing to pack the yaks in the pitch-black night amid their never-ending stream of prayers as the old woman in a nearby tent loudly calls out every deity's name she knows, punctuated with scolding the enemies.

8

You return home from somewhere - maybe from herding, a neighbor's home, or maybe after school. A Chinese Phoenix brand bicycle is parked on its stand in front of your home. It is not your dream bicycle, but you are super happy. It is a big challenge to ride. It is taller than you. A year later, you are tired of finding a place to rest one of your feet when you start and stop the bike, so you cut off the top tube on the frame below the handlebars and near the seat post with a hacksaw without anyone's permission. After that, the bike is unbalanced and unstable when anyone rides it.

9

Six days after an elder neighbor's passing, about 200 local men and boys take the corpse to a small valley in Dur khrod before sunrise. Tamarisks, willows, and shrubs cover the lower part of the valley. The deceased's oldest son and local elders designate a place under a small tree where the corpse is wrapped in white cloth. The son and other relatives prostrate. The rest of us stay far back. After a short time of chanting, the sons and relatives leave. An elder unwraps the white cloth. The corpse is black and stinks. They cut the corpse's back and wait for the vultures to come. They don't. Local elders begin cutting the corpse into small pieces. Some don't wear gloves or chop with knives and swords. Bones with flesh are put on rocks and broken into pieces with sticks. A bad odor permeates the area.

You and others wait for the vultures. Thinking. Life, life's purpose, years and years of struggling with anger, hate, greed, wealth, desire for fame, love, jealousy, cruelty...

10

Autumn pasture. You spend most days with your playmates near a brook. You aren't particularly interested in new clothes but enjoy wearing them to show your playmates once you have some. One of your uncles buys you a pair of brilliantly impressive fake leather shoes in the local monastery town. The next day, you cross a brook while you are playing. Somehow, one of your shoes comes off, and the stream carries it away. You rush after it, but you can't catch it. You cry all that afternoon. Finally, your mother promises she'll buy you another pair. You lose about four pairs of shoes as you play with your peers during those years. You feel terrible and cry in frustration each time.

Several years later, you learn those weren't accidents. A playmate planned it all.

TIBETAN TERMS

bla brang ལྷ་བང།
chos skyong skyabs ཚོས་སྐྱོང་སྐྱལ་པ།
dme shul དམེ་ཤུ།
dur khrod དུར་ཁྲོད།
ldum lhas ལུམ་ལྷས།
reb gong རེབ་གོང།
rnam thar skyid རྣམ་ཐར་སྐྱིད།
sgrol ma mtsho སྐྱོལ་མ་མཚོ།
tshe ring ཚེ་རིང།
zi ling ཟེ་ལིང།

CHINESE TERMS

Qiejiangjia 切江加
Zhongtai 众泰